

re3data.org
REGISTRY OF RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

NFDI4Ing Conference

🔍 2022

NFDI4Ing Conference 2022

How to use re3data – Creating, editing, and analyzing information on research data repositories

Wednesday, October 26th, 10:30 - 12:00

Rouven Schabinger, Dorothea Strecker & Nina Leonie Weisweiler

Schedule

10:30 - 10:45	Introduction to re3data
10:45 - 11:15	The editorial process in re3data, new entries and change requests
11:15 - 11:45	The re3data API: Obtaining and using metadata
11:45 - 12:00	Summary and questions

Registration with CoCalc

If you want to participate in querying the re3data API later in the session, please create an (anonymous) account with CoCalc:

<https://cocalc.com/auth/sign-up>

A **Project Invite Token** will be shared later.

Global Registry
of Research Data
Repositories

re3data.org
REGISTRY OF RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

Search...

Search

across all
research
disciplines

... presents **repositories** for the **permanent storage** and **access** of research data sets to researchers, funding bodies, publishers and scholarly institutions.

...promotes a culture of **sharing, increased access and better visibility** of research data

Number of repositories indexed in re3data per year:

Celebrating 10 Years of re3data

Current Projects:

Partners:

What is a “repository” in re3data?

- We generally refer to all re3data entries as “repositories”.
 - Repositories in re3data are defined as “[...] a subtype of a sustainable information infrastructure providing long-term storage of and access to research data.” ([Metadata Schema for the Description of Research Data Repositories, Version 3.1](#))
- The re3data registration policy is intentionally inclusive to cover a broad range of infrastructures for research data.

The screenshot displays the re3data.org interface for the repository 'Forschungsdatenzentrum im Kraftfahrt-Bundesamt'. The page includes a navigation bar with 'Search', 'Browse', 'Suggest', 'Resources', and 'Contact'. The repository details are organized into sections: 'General', 'Institutions', 'Terms', and 'Standards'. The 'General' section provides the following information:

- Name of repository:** Forschungsdatenzentrum im Kraftfahrt-Bundesamt
- Additional name(s):** FDZ im KBA
- Repository URL:** https://www.kba.de/DE/Statistik/Forschungsdatenzentrum/forschungsdatenzentrum_node.html
- Subject(s):** Traffic and Transport Systems, Logistics; Systems Engineering; Computer Science, Electrical and System Engineering; Engineering Sciences; Human Factors, Ergonomics, Human-Machine Systems
- Description:** The statistics pages of the Kraftfahrt-Bundesamt (KBA) provide an overview of official facts and figures relating to motor vehicles and their users. The data on this page are continuously updated. Publications generally appear as annual statistics. In addition to this, we provide monthly results relating to new registrations and changes of ownership in Germany, as well as information relating to road haulage with German vehicles. The currently provisionally accredited research data center of the Kraftfahrt-Bundesamt extends the data portfolio of the official register data and initially provides anonymised microdata for access to the driving fitness register (FAER). Statistics published by the KBA are available exclusively in German.
- Contact:** fdz@kba.de
- Content type(s):** Standard office documents; Plain text; Scientific and statistical data formats
- Certificates and Standards:** Rat für Sozial- und Wirtschaftsdaten
- Keyword(s):** Register of Driver Fitness - Fahreignungsregister - FAER; drivers; driving licenses; motor vehicles; road haulage; tachograph cards
- Repository type(s):** disciplinary
- Research data repository language(s):** German
- Data and/or service provider:** data provider

At the bottom of the page, there are links for 'Back to search', 'Submit a change request', and 'Get a badge'. A 'Cite this re3data.org record:' section provides the following citation information:

re3data.org: Forschungsdatenzentrum im Kraftfahrt-Bundesamt; editing status 2019-11-08; re3data.org - Registry of Research Data Repositories. <http://doi.org/10.17616/R31NJMNI> last accessed: 2022-10-26

Repositories of NFDI4Ing institutions

As of February 2022, 18 repositories indexed in re3data are affiliated with NFDI4Ing (co-)applicant and participant institutions and also cater to the engineering sciences.

Most of them are institutional repositories.

- maintains repository catering to the engineering sciences
- does not maintain repository catering to the engineering sciences

Registration Policy

Search

Browse ▾

Suggest

Resources ▾

Contact

re3data.org Registration Policy

To be registered in re3data.org a research data repository must

- be run by a legal entity, such as a sustainable institution (e.g. library, university)
- clarify access conditions to the data and repository as well as the terms of use
- **have focus on research data**

A research data repository is a subtype of a sustainable information infrastructure which provides long-term storage and access to research data that is the basis for a scholarly publication. Research data means information objects generated by scholarly projects for example through experiments, measurements, surveys or interviews.

Metadata Schema Version 3.1

Metadata Schema for the Description of Research Data Repositories

Version 3.1, August 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48440/re3.010>

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³ [DataCite - International Data Citation Initiative e.V.](#)

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⁵ [Botanischer Garten und Botanisches Museum Berlin](#), Germany

⁶ [Karlsruher Institut für Technologie / Karlsruhe Institute of Technology \(KIT\)](#), Germany

⁷ [Purdue University](#), United States

Contact
info@re3data.org
<https://www.re3data.org>

42 Properties on...

- General information
- Responsibilities
- Policies
- Legal aspects
- Technical standards
- Quality standards
- DOI for repository descriptions
- Since 2020: ROR IDs for institutions

Version 3.1 of the Metadata Schema:

<https://www.re3data.org/schema>

Icons – facilitating the selection process of appropriate research data repositories

re3data as a metadata provider

re3data is a **central reference point and metadata source** for other service providers, see for example:

- [Open Science Observatory](#)
- [European Open Science Monitor](#)
- [DataCite Commons](#)
- [F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool](#)
- [DARIAH-EU Data Deposit Recommendation Service](#)

re3data coref

COMMUNITY DRIVEN OPEN REFERENCE FOR
RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

Conceptual Service Model

- Embed the registry within the research community and infrastructure landscape to meet the emerging needs for a trusted repository reference.

Metadata Schema

- Revision and enhancement of the re3data metadata schema for the description of research data repositories.

Technical Infrastructure

- Implement new features and the updated metadata schema.
- Provide the necessary technical infrastructure and services

Quality & Transparency

- Conduct a comprehensive study on quality assurances at research data repositories to improve re3data metadata information
- Improve re3data metadata quality, trust and transparency.

Community Building

- Extensive outreach activities, networking and policy development.

Project blog:
coref.project.re3data.org

HELMHOLTZ
Open Science

What makes a good registry record?

Search

Browse ▾

Suggest

Resources ▾

Contact

re3data.org
REGISTRY OF RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

Search...

Search

Rouven Schabinger

Editorial Workflow

Workflow for new repository suggestions and change requests for re3data

Editorial Board

Catherine Jones

Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC)

Jiban K. Pal

Indian Statistical Institute (ISI)

Iris Lindenmann

University of Basel

Rouven Schabinger

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

Angelika Semrau

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

Edeltraud Schnepf

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

Sarah J. Wright

Cornell University

Hui Wang

Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS) / National Science Library (NSL)

Gabriele Weickert

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

Sarah Williams

University of Illinois

Michael Witt

Purdue University

Required information

Required information	
Repository name	<input type="text"/>
Repository name language	<input type="text" value="English"/>
Repository url	<input type="text"/>
Description	<input type="text"/>
Description language	<input type="text" value="English"/>
Data licenses	+ Add dataLicenses
Suggester's email	<input type="text"/>

General

- Additional names
- **Subjects**
- **Repository contacts**
- Content types
- **Certificates**
- Keywords
- **Repository identifiers**
- Size
- **Types**
- Mission statement URL
- Start date
- Repository languages
- Provider types

PANGAEA

Data Publisher for Earth and Environmental Science

<https://www.pangaea.de/>

Oceanography Geology and Palaeontology Geophysics Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Crystallography Biology

Atmospheric Science and Oceanography Geosciences (including Geography) Natural Sciences

Geology and Palaeontology Geophysics and Geodesy Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Crystallography

Life Sciences

The information system PANGAEA is operated as an Open Access library aimed at archiving, publishing and distributing georeferenced data from earth system research. The system guarantees long-term availability of its content through a commitment of the operating institutions.

<https://www.pangaea.de/contact/>

Source code Standard office documents Images Plain text Archived data Audiovisual data

CoreTrustSeal

lithosphere paleontology atmosphere ecology biosphere land surface cryosphere fisheries

agriculture earth science environmental science biology

FAIRsharing_doi:10.25504/FAIRsharing.6yw6cp

disciplinary

<https://www.pangaea.de/about/>

English

data provider

Institutions

- Name
- Name language
- **Country**
- Type
- URL
- Responsibility start date
- Responsibility end date
- Additional names
- Contacts
- Identifiers
- **Responsibility types**

Alfred Wegener Institute - Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research

AWI

Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung

ROR:032e6b942

<https://www.awi.de/en/about-us/service/contact.html>

Germany

general

technical

non-profit

Terms

- Policies
- **Database access**
- **Data accesses**
- **Data uploads**
- Data upload licenses

Policies (2)

Policy Name [CoreTrustSeal assessment](#)

Policy Name [Data policy of the information system PANGAEA](#)

Database access

Type of access to research data repository [open](#)

Database licenses (1)

Database License [CC0](#)

Data access (1)

Type of access to data [open](#)

Data licenses (4)

DataLicense [CC](#)

DataLicense [other](#)

<i>Access (property)</i>	<i>Open Access</i>		<i>Restricted Access</i>		<i>Closed Access</i>
Access to Repository (20.1 databaseAccessType)	open		open or restricted		closed
Access to Data (22.1 dataAccessType)	open (embargoed, restricted, closed)		restricted (embargoed, closed)		closed
Data Upload (24.1 dataUploadType)	open or restricted	closed	open or restricted	closed	-

Standards

- Software
- Versioning
- **PID systems**
- Citation guideline URL
- AID systems
- Enhanced publication
- Quality management
- **APIs**
- **Metadata standards**
- Syndications
- Remarks

DOI

other

yes

<https://wiki.pangaea.de/wiki/Citation>

ORCID

unknown

yes

interfaces (1)

OAI-PMH

Darwin Core

DCC

ISO 19115

DCC

Dublin Core

DCC

DIF - Directory Interchange Format

DCC

Keeping your record up-to-date

- Automated updates (e.g. CTS)
- Reviews by the editorial team
- Your change request?

Contact	https://nanohub.org/about/contact
Content type(s)	Databases Audiovisual data Software applications
Keyword(s)	Nanomaterial Registry nanoBIO nanoscience nan
Persistent identifier(s) of the repository	RRID:SCR_013963 OMICS_27120
Repository size	6.139 resources
Repository type(s)	disciplinary
Mission statement for designated community	https://nanohub.org/about
Research data repository language(s)	English
Data and/or service provider	data provider service provider

[Back to search](#)

[Submit a change request](#)

Submit a change request

Make changes to the properties that need an update. The editorial board will review the submitted record and put it online

General

Repository name	<input type="text" value="nanoHUB"/>
Repository name language	<input type="text" value="English"/>
Additional names	<p>Text <input type="text" value="nanoHUB.org"/></p> <p>Language <input type="text" value="English"/></p>
Repository url	<input type="text" value="https://nanohub.org/"/>
Subjects	<p>Name <input type="text" value="31 Chemistry"/></p> <p>Scheme <input type="text" value="DFG"/></p>

pre-filled
metadata
fields

[Get a badge](#)

Demo Instance

- URL: <https://demo.project.re3data.org>
- Login: re3data.org
- Password: NFDI4Ing2022

Querying the re3data API with R

We will use the platform CoCalc.

1. log in to CoCalc using the account you created earlier
2. click on “projects” in the top left corner
3. enter the **Project Invite Token** in the top right corner:
CLS5VYnBuB7WJTZE
4. start the project **NFDI4Ing Conference 2022**

Querying the re3data API with R

Using Jupyter Notebooks

The screenshot shows a Jupyter Notebook interface. At the top, there is a menu bar with 'File', 'Edit', and 'View'. Below it is a toolbar with various icons, including a 'Run' button (a play icon) which is highlighted with a green box. A green callout box points to the 'Run' button with the text 'run selected cell (or: STRG + ENTER)'. The notebook content includes a title 'data repositories', a subtitle 'NFDI4Ing Conference 2022, 26.10.2022', and a section 'Use case: Identify repositories that a particular institution is i'. Below this is a paragraph of text: 'For a report, all research data repositories operated by KIT are to be identified. Repositories that fulfill this information about these repositories, such as the name or a description.' A section titled 'Step 1: Load packages' follows, with a paragraph: 'The p... exam... selected cell... the HTTP method GET, which will be used to request data from the re3data API. g content of specific elements. If necessary, install the packages before loading'. At the bottom, a code cell is highlighted with a green box, containing the R code:

```
In [1]: library(httr)
library(xml2)
```

Schematic overview of the process

re3data.org
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Any questions?

Stay in touch!

Web: www.re3data.org

Mail: info@re3data.org

Twitter: [@re3data](https://twitter.com/re3data)

Project Blog:

coref.project.re3data.org

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